

(RTS1) and the corresponding genomic clone (RTS2) and a primer extension assay showed that this gene has no introns and a continuous coding region of 285 base pairs yielding a putative polypeptide of 94 amino acids. The coding region of the gene has a 75.8% GC content (216/285). The nucleotide and deduced amino acid sequences, when compared with those in data banks, did not show any significant homology to known sequences. However, GAATTTGTTA, a sequence in the promoter region, differs only by one or two

nucleotides from one of the conserved sequence motifs in the promoter region of two pollen-specific genes of tomato (Twell et al 1991).

The promoter function and regulation of RTS2 for tapetum specificity may be limited to rice. Experiments to obtain rice plants transformed with *gus* A gene-containing constructs under the control of this tapetum-specific promoter are in progress. These studies will allow us to determine the DNA sequences responsible for controlling tapetum-specific expression.

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Production and characterization of *Oryza sativa* L./*O. minuta* Presl. hybrids and backcross progenies

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We attempted to produce hybrid and backcross progenies between rice and wild species to enable the transfer of some important traits from *O. minuta* into locally cultivated rice.

Rice varieties Mahsuri, Setanjung, MR84, and MR103 were crossed with one accession of *O. minuta* (IRRI Acc. 101141), which also served as the male parent. The original F₁ hybrids and two colchicine-treated F₁s were then backcrossed to the respective *O. sativa* varieties as the recurrent parent to produce backcross 1 (BC₁). Successive backcrosses to the recurrent parents were made to produce BC₂ progenies.

Seeds of the F₁, BC₁, and BC₂ with poorly developed endosperm began to degenerate 2 wk after pollination. To ensure survival of the hybrids and BC progenies, the 14-d-old embryos were rescued on 1/4 MS medium following the procedure of Jena and Khush (1984).

Morphological characteristics, pollen fertility, somatic chromosome number, and meiotic chromosome pairing of the F₁ hybrids and BC progenies were observed.

The hybrids and BC progenies were also subjected to starch gel electrophoresis and stained for shikimate dehydrogenase (SDH), phosphogluconate dehydrogenase (PGD), and glutamate oxaloacetate transaminase (GOT) activities using the procedure described by Glaszmann et al (1988).

Seed set in *O. sativa/O. minuta* crosses ranged from 9.5 to 25.1%, depending on the rice variety used (see table). By rescuing 10- to 14-d-old embryos, 414 F₁ hybrids were successfully raised to maturity. The hybrids closely resembled their wild parent, although some of their morphological characteristics were intermediate. The male sterile F₁ plants were vigorous and tillered profusely. All had the expected chromosome number (2n=3x=36) and showed irregular meiotic chromosome pairing, with mostly univalents. Mean chromosome configuration was 29.31 (16-

36) Is + 3.32 (0-10)IIs + 0.02 (0-1)IIIs + 0.002(0-1)IVs.

Seed set in the original F₁ backcrossed with *O. sativa* parents was extremely low (0.03%); however, seed set was slightly higher (0.88%) when backcrosses were done on the colchicine-treated plants (see table). The 17 BC₁ plants obtained after embryo rescue appeared more like the F₁ and were male sterile. These plants, for which chromosome numbers varied from 44 to 48, exhibited irregular meiosis with mostly univalents.

Seed set in BC₂ was about 2.4% (see table). Of the 47 embryos cultured, 18 BC₂ plants grew to maturity and had different morphological characteristics, pollen fertility, and somatic chromosome number. Of these, one plant closely resembled the *O. sativa* parent and had 24 chromosomes. The partially fertile plant had about 58.8% pollen stainability and 12.47% spikelet fertility and showed 12 bivalents in 60% of the cells and 9-11 bivalents in the other 40% of the cells. The results showed the recovery of *O. sativa* phenotype in the

Production of *Oryza sativa/O. minuta* F₁ hybrids and backcross progenies.

Cross combination ^a	Spikelets pollinated (no.)	Seed set (%)	Embryos cultured (no.)	Plants obtained (no.)	Chromosome number (2n)
Mahsuri/ <i>O. minuta</i> (F ₁)	1,742	15.1	132	108	36
Setanjung/ <i>O. minuta</i> (F ₁)	1,729	25.1	138	123	36
MR84/ <i>O. minuta</i> (F ₁)	2,465	12.5	110	89	36
MR103/ <i>O. minuta</i> (F ₁)	2,346	9.5	112	94	36
(<i>O. sativa/O. minuta</i>) × <i>O. sativa</i> (BC ₁)	37,080	0.03	10	1	45
(CT F ₁)/ <i>O. sativa</i> (BC ₁)	3,733	0.88	33	16	44-48
(BC ₁ from CT F ₁) × <i>O. sativa</i> (BC ₂)	4,452	2.47	110	32 (18) ^a	24-37

^a CT F₁ = colchicine-treated F₁ (*O. sativa/O. minuta*). Figure in parentheses shows number of plants with normal growth.

second backcross, which probably resulted from the restricted recombination between parental genomes indicated by the low frequency of rod bivalents in the meiosis of the F₁ hybrids. Furthermore, none of the *O. minuta* allozyme (*Sdh1*, *Pgd2*, *Got1*, and *Got3*) was detected in the 24-chromosome plant, indicating lack of introgression of chromosome segment from the donor wild species.

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Histological observation of callus morphology in rice

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We evaluated callus morphology, emphasizing cell compositions of rice varieties, through histological observation.

Callus morphology of five indica (IR54, Rc2, Oboshi, 2757, 2764), two japonica (Nipponbare, Tsutsu), and two javanica (Lemonte, Rinatte) varieties was evaluated in two callus induction media. Varieties showing good callus growth 2 and 4 wk after culture were evaluated through histological observations using scanning electron and light microscopes.

Of the varieties tested, IR54, Toboshi, Nipponbare, Tsutsu, and Rinatte exhibited good callus growth. Callus morphology of each subspecies differed from one another. At 2 wk after culture, calli of IR54 and Toboshi were characterized by two callus masses: one was yellow, compact, and smooth-surfaced; the other yellowish with hairy protuberance and green spots. Japonica varieties Nipponbare and Tsutsu and javanica variety Rinatte had almost similar morphology. Calli of both sub-

1. Dehusked grains of a) indica (IR54), japonica (Nipponbare), and javanica (Rinatte) and b) their corresponding callus types.

species were yellowish, compact, and smooth-surfaced. Slight changes in callus morphology were noted 1 mo after culture. Green spots occupied more than 50% of the whole callus mass in IR54. Calli of Nipponbare and Tsutsu became globular and easily disintegrated into small pieces. Callus of Rinatte became friable. Callus types of the three subspecies represented by IR54, Nipponbare, and Rinatte are shown in Figure 1b.

Histological observation through a scanning electron microscope showed that

2. Scanning electron microscopic observation of the cell compositions in the calli of a) IR54, b) Nipponbare, and c) Rinatte. Scale bars = 300 μ.

Genetic analysis of epicuticular structure involving a dripping-wet leaf mutant of rice

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We obtained a dripping-wet leaf mutant among doubled haploid progenies regenerated from rice (*Oryza sativa* L. cv Nipponbare) anther culture. This mutant

each callus type had a distinct cell composition (Fig. 2a-c). Callus of IR54 showed a large, highly compact cell mass with domelike structures. The surface was rough with corrugations (Fig. 2a). Callus of Nipponbare was made up of compact, globular cell masses of about the same size (Fig. 2b). The cell masses were composed of round cells arranged in layers, like a flower. Callus of Rinatte was composed of small, round, compactly arranged cells (Fig. 2c). Light microscopic observation of the resin sections generally showed darkly stained, meristematic cell clusters.

The results of a study using mungbean suggest that cell types in a callus mass relate to embryogenic potential (Narciso and Hattori 1995). This relationship has not been fully studied in rice. Results of this research could provide the basic information needed to establish this relationship.

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was derived from callus treated with 20 Gy of gamma rays 2 d after transfer to regeneration medium. Rice leaves, in general, can shed drops of water; however, leaves of the dripping-wet leaf mutant do not because of their highly hydrophilic leaf surface. Many of these mutant types, which are controlled by a single recessive gene, have been obtained in rice. Some of these gene loci have already been identified (Sato et al 1983). Although factors causing high leaf wettability in these mutants are not clear, leaf surface structure